

The Effect of Electronic Word of Mouth on Purchase Intention: The Mediating Role of Brand Image and Trust in the Context of Mykonos Perfume Products

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of electronic word of mouth (E-WOM) on purchase intention with brand image and trust as mediating variables in the context of Mykonos perfume products. The study is based on the rapid growth of local perfume brands in digital markets, where consumers frequently rely on online reviews, ratings, and recommendations before purchasing fragrance products. A quantitative approach was applied using survey data from 215 respondents who were familiar with Mykonos products. The data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS). The findings show that E-WOM has a positive and significant effect on brand image, trust, and purchase intention. Brand image and trust also have positive and significant effects on purchase intention. Furthermore, brand image and trust significantly mediate the relationship between E-WOM and purchase intention. These results indicate that consumer-generated information in digital media can strengthen favorable brand perceptions, reduce perceived uncertainty, and encourage purchase intention. The study contributes to digital marketing literature by emphasizing the role of psychological mechanisms in transforming online communication into consumer purchase intention, particularly for local perfume products sold through e-commerce

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, the perfume industry in Indonesia continues to grow rapidly in line with changes in consumer lifestyles and the increasing use of online shopping platforms. Perfume is no longer considered merely a personal care product, but has also become part of self-expression, confidence, and personal identity. The growth of e-commerce has provided greater opportunities for local perfume brands to reach consumers more widely through digital channels. As competition becomes more intense, perfume brands are required to develop effective digital marketing strategies in order to attract consumers and strengthen their position in the market.

Mykonos is one of the local perfume brands that has shown significant development since its introduction in 2019. By utilizing digital platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, Shopee, and other online marketplaces, Mykonos has successfully expanded its market reach and increased consumer awareness. In online perfume purchasing, consumers usually cannot directly test or smell the product

before buying it. As a result, many consumers depend on online information such as reviews, ratings, recommendations, and experiences shared by other users. This condition makes Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM) an important factor in helping consumers evaluate products and reduce uncertainty before making a purchase.

The role of E-WOM in shaping purchase intention is not limited to its direct influence, but can also occur through brand image and trust. Positive reviews and recommendations shared online can create a favorable perception of a brand, making consumers view the brand as attractive, credible, and relevant to their needs. In addition, trust becomes an essential factor in online transactions because consumers cannot physically assess the product before purchasing. When consumers believe that Mykonos has a positive brand image and can provide reliable product quality, their intention to purchase is likely to increase. Therefore, this study aims to examine the influence of E-WOM on purchase intention, with brand image and trust as mediating variables in the context of Mykonos perfume

products. This research is expected to provide empirical evidence on how online consumer communication can shape brand perception, build trust, and encourage purchase intention in the local perfume industry.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Purchase Intention

Purchase intention refers to the consumer's tendency or willingness to buy a product after evaluating several available alternatives. According to Kotler and Keller (2016), purchase intention is formed when consumers compare different brands and develop a preference for the brand that best meets their needs and desires. In this process, consumers do not make decisions impulsively, but consider information, benefits, and product suitability before intending to purchase. Ferdinand (2002) explains that purchase intention can be measured through transactional intention, referential intention, preferential intention, and exploratory intention, which reflect the consumer's desire to buy, recommend, prefer, and seek further information about a product.

B. Brand Image

Brand image is the overall perception that consumers have toward a brand, which is developed through the information they receive, their experiences, and the marketing messages delivered by the company. Kotler and Keller (2016) state that brand image plays an important role in differentiating a brand from its competitors and shaping a positive impression in consumers' minds. When a brand has a strong and favorable image, consumers are more likely to feel interested, develop emotional attachment, and show a higher intention to purchase. According to Juliani Leliga (2012), brand image can be assessed through three indicators, namely brand strength, brand favorability, and brand uniqueness, which describe the extent to which a brand is easily recognized, positively perceived, and has distinctive characteristics compared to other brands.

C. Trust

Trust is the consumer's belief in a brand that is developed through the information, knowledge, and experiences they have obtained about the product. Mowen and Minor (2002) explain that trust emerges when consumers perceive a brand as dependable, honest, and capable of delivering the benefits they expect. In the purchasing process, trust is essential because it helps reduce doubt and increases consumers' sense of security. When consumers have confidence in a brand, they tend to feel more certain and are more likely to show purchase intention. According to Yee and Faziharudean (2010), trust can be evaluated through three indicators, namely integrity, benevolence, and ability.

D. Electronic Word of Mouth

Electronic word of mouth (E-WOM) refers to the exchange of information, opinions, experiences, and recommendations among consumers through digital platforms. Gruen et al. (2006) explain that E-WOM allows consumers to share their experiences about products or services even without knowing each other personally. Compared to traditional word of mouth, E-WOM has a wider reach and spreads more quickly through the internet, making it an important part of digital marketing strategies. Syafaruddin et al. (2016) state that E-WOM occurs when consumers voluntarily share information and experiences online to help others make purchasing decisions. According to Goyette et al. (2010), E-WOM can be measured through three dimensions: intensity, valence of opinion, and content, which describe how often consumers share information, whether the opinions are positive or negative, and the quality of information provided about a product.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study used a quantitative approach because it tested the relationship among variables through numerical data and statistical analysis (Sugiyono, 2019). The research object was Mykonos perfume consumers in Indonesia. The population was categorized as infinite because the exact number of Mykonos consumers cannot be determined precisely. The sample was selected using purposive sampling, with the criterion that respondents had purchased Mykonos products at least once.

The study used primary data collected through an online questionnaire distributed using Google Form. A total of 215 responses were used in the analysis. Each item was measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The research model consisted of E-WOM as the independent variable, purchase intention as the dependent variable, and brand image and trust as mediating variables. The operational indicators were adopted from established measurements, including purchase intention indicators from Ferdinand, brand image indicators from Juliani Leliga, trust indicators from Yee and Faziharudean, and E-WOM indicators from Goyette et al. (Ferdinand, 2002; Juliani Leliga, 2012; Yee & Faziharudean, 2010; Goyette et al., 2010).

The data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) with SmartPLS 4.0. The measurement model was evaluated through convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability, while the structural model was evaluated through R-square, Q-square, F-square, path coefficient, and specific indirect effects. Following PLS-SEM reporting guidelines, the hypotheses were supported when the t-statistic was greater than 1.96 and the p-value was below 0.05 (Hair et al., 2019)

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IV. RESULT

To evaluate the research model, the PLS model was first estimated using the algorithm technique available in SEM-PLS. This estimation process was carried out to obtain the values required for assessing both the measurement model and the structural model. Through this stage, the relationships between latent variables and their indicators, as well as the relationships among the constructs, could be examined systematically. The results generated from the algorithm estimation serve as the basis for determining the validity, reliability, and explanatory power of the model. Therefore, the following section presents the results of the SEM-PLS estimation after the model was processed using the algorithm procedure.

Table 1. Average Variance Extracted Values

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
E-WOM (X)	0.570
Brand Image (Z1)	0.704
Purchase Intention (Y)	0.698
Trust (Z2)	0.657

Based on the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values, all constructs have values above 0.5. This indicates that the constructs meet the criteria for convergent validity, meaning that the indicators adequately explain their respective latent variables and the measurement model is suitable for further analysis.

Table 2. Result of Construct Reliability and Validity Test

	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Z1	0.826	0.704
X	0.841	0.570
Y	0.822	0.698
Z2	0.791	0.657

The construct reliability and validity results show that all composite reliability values exceed 0.70, while all AVE values are higher than 0.50. These results indicate that the indicators consistently represent the latent variables, and the model can be considered reliable and valid.

Table 3. R-Square Value

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Brand Image (Z1)	0.187	0.183
Purchase Intention (Y)	0.393	0.385
Trust (Z2)	0.154	0.150

The R-Square value for Purchase Intention (Y) is 0.393, indicating that 39.3% of the variation in purchase intention can be explained by E-WOM, Brand Image, and Trust, while the remaining 60.7% is influenced by other factors outside the model. Brand Image (Z1) has an R-Square value of 0.187, while Trust (Z2) has an R-Square value of 0.154. Overall, the model shows explanatory power for the endogenous variables in the study.

Table 4. Path Coefficient Result

	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Z1 -> Y	0.279	4.105	0.000
X -> Z1	0.432	6.397	0.000
X -> Y	0.253	3.668	0.000
X -> Z2	0.393	6.765	0.000
Z2 -> Y	0.275	3.608	0.000

Based on the results of the path coefficient test, it can be explained that all direct relationships among the variables in this research model have positive and significant effects. The relationship between E-WOM and Brand Image shows a coefficient value of 0.432, a T-statistics value of 6.397, and a P-value of 0.000. These results indicate that E-WOM has a positive and significant effect on Brand Image. This means that the higher the quality of electronic word of mouth received by consumers, such as reviews, recommendations, comments, and product-related discussions on digital platforms, the stronger the Brand Image formed in consumers' perceptions. Furthermore, E-WOM also has a positive and significant effect on Trust with a coefficient value of 0.393. This finding indicates that information and experiences shared by other consumers through online media can increase consumer confidence in the brand. In addition, E-WOM has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention with a coefficient value of 0.253. This shows that online information obtained by consumers can encourage their intention to purchase the product.

The results also show that Brand Image and Trust have positive and significant effects on Purchase Intention. This means that consumers' intention to purchase tends to increase when they have a positive perception of the brand and trust the brand's ability to fulfill their expectations. Among all direct relationships, the strongest effect is found in the relationship between E-WOM and Brand Image. This indicates that E-WOM plays an important role in shaping consumer perceptions of Mykonos. Positive reviews, recommendations, and discussions from other consumers can help strengthen the image of the brand, especially for perfume products, where consumers often rely on online information before making a purchase decision. Therefore, it can be concluded that Purchase Intention is not only directly influenced by E-WOM, but also indirectly strengthened

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through Brand Image and Trust as psychological factors that support consumers' intention to buy.

Table 5. Indirect Effect Result

	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
X -> Z1 -> Y	0.120	3.403	0.001
X -> Z2 -> Y	0.108	3.032	0.002

The indirect effect test shows that the path E-WOM (X) -> Brand Image (Z1) -> Purchase Intention (Y) has a coefficient of 0.120, a T-statistics value of 3.403, and a P-value of 0.001. Furthermore, the path E-WOM (X) -> Trust (Z2) -> Purchase Intention (Y) has a coefficient of 0.108, a T-statistics value of 3.032, and a P-value of 0.002. These values indicate that both Brand Image and Trust significantly mediate the effect of E-WOM on Purchase Intention.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that 1) E-WOM has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention; 2) E-WOM has a positive and significant effect on Brand Image; 3) E-WOM has a positive and significant effect on Trust; 4) Brand Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention; 5) Trust has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention; 6) Brand Image mediates the effect of E-WOM on Purchase Intention; and 7) Trust mediates the effect of E-WOM on Purchase Intention. These findings show that positive online communication about Mykonos perfume can strengthen consumer perceptions, build trust, and increase purchase intention in digital marketplaces.

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